

rice mitochondria and their nature can be shown with the help of the lectins.

We used the concanavalin A (Con A) gold conjugates. This lectin has sugar specificity: D-mannose > D-glucose > N-acetyl D-glucosamine. Rice mitochondria were isolated, fixed, incubated in 20% Con A gold conjugate solution in

phosphate buffered saline (PBS), and studied under an electron microscope.

The rice mitochondrion surface membrane binds the Con A gold conjugate (i.e., contains Con A receptors, probably D-mannose) (Fig. 1, 2). When stained with Os, the rice mitochondrion surface looks as if it consists of global

grains. This is probably the result of protein structure distribution.

The golden deposits structure looks like a ramified tree. Evidently this is connected with the fact that the lectin carbohydrate receptors are parts of the polymer chains. ■

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Performance of *Sesbania rostrata* in calcareous soils

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We compared the performance of stem- and root-nodulating *S. rostrata*, a newly introduced green manure (GM) crop, and *S. aculeata*, the GM crop commonly grown in Bihar, with different levels of inorganic fertilizer in an irrigated ricefield during 1987-89 wet season (May-Dec).

Soils were silt-loam with pH 8.5, 0.60% organic C, and 272-16-119 kg available NPK/ha.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. GM crops were broadcast the third week of May at 30 kg seed/ha. When needed, 17.6 kg P/ha was basal applied. To ensure germination, one irrigation was applied 5 d before sowing.

The GM crops were incorporated 45 d after sowing; on the same day, 35- to 40-d-old seedlings of 150-d-duration

rice variety Radha were transplanted. K was basal applied at 16.6 kg/ha in all plots. P and N were applied per treatment (see table).

GM plant stands were uniform in all plots. Dry matter production and N yield were estimated at incorporation.

S. rostrata added more dry matter and N than *S. aculeata* in all treatments. P

applied at sowing of GM crops was superior to P applied at puddling.

Highest grain yields (3.1-3.3 ma) were with recommended fertilizers; with *S. rostrata* plus P and 40 kg N/ha in two equal splits; and with *S. aculeata* plus P and 40 kg N/ha in two equal splits. Straw yields with these treatments followed the same trend. Net returns were higher with *S. rostrata* plus P and N. ■

Effect of GM crops on rice yield and net return per rupee of investment on pooled (1987, 1988, and 1989) basis, Bihar, India.

Treatment ^a	Dry matter from GM (t/ha)	N accumulated (kg/ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)		Net return
			Grain	Straw	
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i> + P + 40 kg N/ha in 2 equal splits: MT + PI	4.2	76.2	3.1	5.1	1.10
<i>S. aculeata</i> + no P + 40 kg N/ha in 2 equal splits: MT + PI	4.0	72.4	2.8	4.7	1.08
<i>S. rostrata</i> + P + 40 kg N/ha in 2 equal splits: MT + PI	4.3	81.5	3.3	5.5	1.24
<i>S. rostrata</i> + no P + 40 kg N/ha in 2 equal splits: MT + PI	4.0	75.0	2.9	4.8	1.15
40 kg N/ha in 2 equal splits: MT + PI	-	-	2.4	3.9	0.71
80-40-20 kg NPK/ha	-	-	3.3	5.4	1.20
<i>S. aculeata</i> + recommended 40-20 kg PK/ha	4.0	12.3	2.4	4.0	0.85
<i>S. rostrata</i> + recommended 40-20 kg PK/ha	4.1	16.4	2.5	4.2	0.93
Control (no GM, no NPK)	-	-	1.8	2.8	0.51
LSD (0.05)	-	-	0.3	0.4	0.12

^aMT = maximum tillering, PI = panicle initiation, GM = green manure.

Integrated pest management—diseases

Kresek in mature rice plants

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We found kresek in mature rice plants during 1990 in rainfed lowland fields at the BRRI Regional Station experimental farm and in farmers' fields in Barisal. This is the first report of this disease in Bangladesh.

Infested tiller showing normal older leaves and leaf sheaths.

The first symptom appears in the youngest leaf as dense whitish stripes or lesions at the base of the leaf blade. This whitish lesion moves upward through the midrib, which turns brown. Gradually, the leaf turns yellow and rolls along the midrib. It looks like deadheart caused by stem borer, but the dead leaf cannot be pulled up easily. Older leaves and leaf sheaths remain normal and green (see figure).

When a diseased tiller is split, the entire leaf base enclosed by the older leaf sheath appears soft and rotten and

has a very strong, unpleasant odor. Leaves developing later seldom pass through the damaged leaf base, but are malformed. In some cases, the entire tiller becomes damaged, turns dark brown, looks rotten, and has an unpleasant odor.

Disease symptoms were confined mostly to plants between tillering to boot. Seedlings that show kresiek symptoms die within a week or two; infected mature tillers do not die. In farmers' fields, almost all varieties or lines were infected, with less intensity in local varieties and higher in BR11 (see table). ■

Rice entries severely infected with kresiek at the mature plant stage in rainfed lowland fields at BRRI Regional Station, Barisal, 1990.

Designation	Infected hills (%)	Infected tillers (%)	Designation	Infected hills (%)	Infected tillers (%)
Affakilombero-1-96	90	33	BRB468-33-2-2	100	24
B5986-MR-B-1-10	100	46	BRB468-33-3-1	100	31
BR11	100	49	BRB468-33-3-2	100	24
BR23	70	36	BRB489-22-2-2	100	26
BR850-9-1-1	90	36	BRB489-51-3-2	100	27
BR1244-9-1-2-1-1	80	30	BRB489-53-1-4	100	23
BR1711-27-3-2-2	80	32	BRB489-58-2-6	90	28
BR1728-26-1-1-5	90	30	BRB489-60-1-9	90	29
BRB398-26-1-3	90	31	BRB498-6-B	100	23

Integrated pest management—insects

Influence of changing cropping pattern on insect pests of deepwater rice

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The traditional cropping pattern in deepwater rice (DWR) areas of Bangladesh is single DWR or mixed DWR + aus (summer rice) followed by nonrice rabi (winter) crops or fallow. During the last two decades, irrigated modern variety (MV) boro (winter rice) rice has been grown in about 0.8 million ha of the 2.0 million ha DWR area. In many DWR areas, boro - fallow or boro - rabi crops has become the dominant cropping pattern.

We compared the incidence in DWR of insect pests, particularly yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas*, in boro rice-dominant and DWR-dominant sites in central Bangladesh in early Jul 1988, when DWR was at the early elongation stage and aus rice was either at the ripening stage or harvested. YSB incidence was estimated by dissecting about 100 DWR stems from each site. Incidence of other pests was recorded.

YSB, hispa beetle *Dicladispa armigera*, and long-horned cricket *Euscyrtus concinnus* were moderate to severe at some sites (see table). In boro rice sites, stem borer (SB) damage to DWR was about six times greater than at the DWR or nonboro rice sites (see figure; $p < 0.01$, t-test on square root transformed data).

Of the 60 borer larvae and pupae found during stem dissections, 97% were YSB and the rest (3%) dark-headed borer *Chilo polychrysa*. Larvae and pupae populations were significantly higher at the boro rice sites (9.88/100 stems) than at the nonboro rice sites (0.56/100 stems, $p < 0.01$, t-test on square root transformed data). Correlation was positive between the presence of a boro crop in DWR areas and SB damage levels ($r = 0.618$, $p < 0.05$, $df = 14$).

Hispa activity was also higher in boro crop areas. Hispa incidence appeared higher in single-crop DWR fields than in mixed aus + DWR fields; the opposite was true of long-horned cricket incidence. Correlation was negative between aus +

Population densities of yellow stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* Walker in DWR and levels of damaged stems in boro-dominant and non-boro deepwater rice locations, July 1988, Bangladesh. Boro =

Incidence of 3 insect pests in deepwater rice in selected areas in Bangladesh, 1988.^a

Location	Dominant rice crop in the area	Present rice crop	Stem borer		Hispa beetle ^b	Long-horned cricket ^b
			Damaged stems (%)	Population (no./100 stems)		
Lowhajang	DWR	DWR	0	0	M-S	Minor
Sherajdikhan	Boro	DWR	14.3	7	M-S	Minor
Mirzapur	Boro	Aus + DWR	21.9	7	Minor	M-S
Basail	DWR	Aus + DWR	1.7	0	Minor	M-S
Kalihati	DWR	Aus+DWR	1.2	0	Minor	Minor
Kalihati	Boro	DWR	2.4	1	M-S	Minor
Rupganj	Boro	DWR	2.8	2	M-S	Minor
Rupganj	DWR	DWR	0	0	Minor	Minor
Narshingdi	DWR	DWR	1.3	1	Minor	Minor
Polash	Boro	DWR	21.5	13	Minor	Minor
Arihazar	DWR	DWR	2.7	0	Minor	Minor
Dhamrai	Boro	Aus + DWR	12.5	3	Minor	M-S
Dhamrai	DWR	Aus+DWR	1.5	0	Minor	M-S
Shibalaya	DWR	Aus + DWR	11.7	3	Minor	M-S
Manikganj	DWR	Aus+DWR	3.3	1	Minor	Minor
Joydebpur	Boro	DWR	34.3	36	Minor	Minor

^aDWR = deepwater rice, aus = summer rice, boro = winter rice. ^bM-S = moderate-severe.